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Abstract

Urban green spaces have a beneficial effect on the health and well-being of citizens. The features of such spaces and users' satisfaction with them determine the type and frequency of activities conducted inside parks. Understanding the relationships among these aspects is important for promoting adequate designs for these spaces. On the other hand, the limited availability of urban surface area in many cities determines the size of parks. The effect of size on people's satisfaction and their use of parks is an aspect that has not been studied in depth in the scientific literature. Therefore, this study aimed to examine the relationships between citizens' perceptions of the parks' features and their uses as a function of their size. For this purpose, surveys were conducted in large and small green spaces. The results showed the importance of considering noise in the management of both types of parks to improve overall satisfaction. In addition, overall satisfaction was related to visual aspects (conservation) in large parks, and social aspects (safety and users) in small parks. Suitably designed canine and play areas in large parks and functionality for the streets surrounding small parks can contribute to reducing noise annoyance. This study showed that the size of green spaces has a positive correlation with the frequency of walking, exercising and relaxing. Furthermore, improving some environmental features would also help to increase the frequency of these activities. In this regard, the existence of groves played an important role in promoting physical activity in both types of parks, and the quality of the air and the absence of noise contributed to relaxation in large parks.

Keywords	health; noise; park features; small parks; social and physical activities; urban management
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Highlights

- Study of users' perception as a useful tool for the design of urban green spaces
- Noise explained the greatest variability of overall satisfaction with parks
- Road traffic was significantly more annoying in small parks
- Walking, relaxing, and exercising positively correlated with the park area
- Positive correlation found between groves and exercising in both types of parks

Perceptions and use of urban green spaces on the basis of size

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Perceptions and use of urban green spaces on the basis of size

Abstract

Urban green spaces have a beneficial effect on the health and well-being of citizens. The features of such spaces and users' satisfaction with them determine the type and frequency of activities conducted inside parks. Understanding the relationships among these aspects is important for promoting adequate designs for these spaces. On the other hand, the limited availability of urban surface area in many cities determines the size of parks. The effect of size on people's satisfaction and their use of parks is an aspect that has not been studied in depth in the scientific literature. Therefore, this study aimed to examine the relationships between citizens' perceptions of the parks' features and their uses as a function of their size. For this purpose, surveys were conducted in large and small green spaces. The results showed the importance of considering noise in the management of both types of parks to improve overall satisfaction. In addition, overall satisfaction was related to visual aspects (conservation) in large parks, and social aspects (safety and users) in small parks. Suitably designed canine and play areas in large parks and functionality for the streets surrounding small parks can contribute to reducing noise annoyance. This study showed that the size of green spaces has a positive correlation with the frequency of walking, exercising and relaxing. Furthermore, improving some environmental features would also help to increase the frequency of these activities. In this regard, the existence of groves played an important role in promoting physical activity in both types of parks, and the quality of the air and the absence of noise contributed to relaxation in large parks.

Keywords: health; noise; park features; small parks; social and physical activities; urban management

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62 **1. Introduction**
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64

65 Population growth in cities will bring environmental, social and health challenges
66 (UN, 2017). Green spaces play an important role in modulating human health and social
67 well-being in the urban environment (Bedimo-Rung et al., 2005).
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69 The presence of urban green spaces in cities generates economic and environmental
70 benefits. Urban green spaces help to improve air quality (Escobedo et al., 2011; James et
71 al., 2015), reduce the urban heat island effect (Shisegar, 2014), mitigate runoff (Zhang et
72 al., 2015), reduce healthcare costs (Cox et al., 2017), increase property values for homes
73 that are nearby or overlook them (Morancho, 2003), maintain urban biodiversity (Fontana
74 et al., 2011), promote green spaces as tourist destinations, and generate revenue (Jim and
75 Chen, 2006).
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77 Specifically analysing the direct benefits of green spaces to citizens, numerous
78 studies show that the presence of parks in residential areas increases social contact and
79 cohesion (Peters et al., 2010; Dadvand et al., 2016) and decreases stress (Nieuwenhuijsen
80 et al., 2017). Their presence also promotes physical activity and may be linked with
81 greater health benefits than in other settings (Mitchell and Popham, 2008; Vujcic et al.,
82 2018).
83

84 Research has shown the positive influence of quiet urban areas as a possible measure
85 to mitigate the effect of noise (Öhrström et al., 2006). However, some studies (Cohen et
86 al., 2014; Tse et al., 2012) show that noise levels in urban green spaces are significantly
87 higher than values recommended by the European Environmental Agency (EEA) for
88 quiet areas (EEA, 2014). Koprowska et al. (2018) conclude that noise levels have the
89 biggest influence on noise perception, even though people feel less annoyed by noise
90 when surrounded by greenery (Cassina et al., 2017; Dzhambov et al., 2018). Although
91 there are different sources of urban noise (Bunn and Zannin, 2016; Gagliardi et al., 2018;
92 Bernardini et al., 2019), road traffic is the largest source of noise pollution (WHO, 2018).
93 Prolonged exposure to noise can have negative effects on health, such as sleep
94 disturbances (Halperin, 2014), annoyance (Miedema and Oudshoorn, 2001),
95 cardiovascular diseases (Babisch, 2014), and learning impairment (Klatte et al., 2013).
96 Thus, noise studies have been conducted around different aspects in urban environments:
97 sampling strategies (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2018), sound sources (Barrigón Morillas et
98 al., 2013), noise monitoring (Zambon et al., 2018), action plans (Licitra et al., 2017) or
99 noise mitigation (Fredianelli et al, 2019).
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121 58 Literature reviews conducted by Bedimo-Rung et al. (2005) and McCormack et al.
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123 59 (2010) show that the relationship between green-space use and health is well established,
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125 60 but research establishing a relationship between features of green spaces and the
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127 61 frequency of their use is lacking. These literature reviews have been cited recently,
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129 62 highlighting this deficiency in the literature (Triguero-Mas et al., 2015; Vujcic et al.,
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131 63 2018). Determination of green-space features that influence how often a certain activity
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133 64 is conducted constitutes useful information for urban planners and managers. This
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135 65 information allows for the configuration of an optimal environment to promote certain
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137 66 activities with health benefits. User perceptions of green-space features is used as a
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139 67 predictor of the presence and the quality of these characteristics (Dadvand et al., 2016;
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141 68 Kothencz and Blaschke, 2017). Dadvand et al. (2016) suggest that perceived availability
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143 69 of green spaces could be a better predictor than physical availability.

140 70 In addition, user characteristics such as age, education, and gender may relate to the
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142 71 use of green spaces (Bedimo-Rung et al., 2005). However, the relatively unchangeable
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144 72 nature of these demographic characteristics has led to an increased focus on green-space
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146 73 features that are modifiable (Schipperijn et al., 2010).

147 74 The presence and quality of urban green spaces should be considered in urban design.
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149 75 A recent World Health Organization (WHO) report provides evidence of public health
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151 76 benefits in relation to green-space access, and encourages urban managers to increase
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153 77 these spaces (WHO, 2016). The WHO recommends between 10 and 15 m² of green area
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155 78 per inhabitant (Brebba et al., 2010). However, finding space for new parks is often
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157 79 difficult in increasingly dense cities. Smaller public green areas may perhaps provide
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159 80 some of the desired green space, increasing the availability of urban green spaces in this
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161 81 manner. Additionally, because of their smaller size, these green areas could be close to
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163 82 people's homes. The accessibility of green spaces will influence their use (Schipperijn et
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165 83 al., 2010; Wang et al., 2015). In this context, studies conducted in small parks about how
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167 84 people use and perceive green spaces are relevant (Peschardt et al., 2012, 2014; Brown et
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169 85 al., 2018).

166 86 The main objective of this study was to analyse the features and uses of two groups
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168 87 of green spaces having different sizes. The features of urban green spaces were evaluated
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170 88 through the perceptions of users. For this, some research questions were addressed and
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172 89 grouped as follows.

172 90 Questions that analyse the features of the parks, how they are perceived, and user
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174 91 satisfaction with them:

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180 92 Q1. Do the two types of green spaces differ in users' overall satisfaction and in
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182 93 satisfaction with their features?

183 94 Q2. What is the relationship between the perception of features and overall
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185 95 satisfaction with the green spaces?

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187 96 Question that analyses the annoyance caused by different usual sound sources in
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189 97 urban parks:

190 98 Q3. Do the two types of green spaces differ in how users perceive the annoyance
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192 99 caused by different sources of noise?

193 100 Questions that analyse the uses of parks and their relationship with their features:

194 101 Q4. Do the two types of green spaces differ in the frequency of activities conducted
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196 102 by users?

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198 103 Q5. Is there any relationship between the frequency of these activities and the size of
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200 104 the green spaces?

201 105 Q6. Is the relationship between satisfaction with park features and the frequency of
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203 106 activities different for large parks than for small parks?

204 107 The answers to these questions are important in determining the features of green
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206 108 spaces that would help urban planners to improve citizen satisfaction and use. These
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208 109 features may differ depending on the size of the park.

211 110 **2. Methodology**

212 213 214 111 *2.1. Selection of urban green spaces*

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216 112 The city of Cáceres was an optimal place for this study. Cáceres is located in
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218 113 southwest Spain and has 19.8 m² of green space per capita
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220 114 (<http://sig.caceres.es/?lang=en>). This value is one of the highest in the country (Fuller and
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222 115 Gaston, 2009). In 2014, Cáceres had an approximate population of 96,500.

223 116 Parks of different sizes close to the city centre (distance < 1.5 km) and emblematic
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225 117 of each district were selected for this study (Fig. 1). These green spaces are close to the
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227 118 population residing in the districts (distance < 1 km). The accessibility of green spaces is
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229 119 taken into account when considering their use (Schipperijn et al., 2017; Wang et al.,
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231 120 2015).

232 121 The green spaces were classified into two groups based on their size:

- 233 122 - Large urban green spaces: Príncipe (22.0 ha) and Rodeo (10.6 ha).

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239 123 - Small urban green spaces: Valhondo (2.2 ha), Fernando Turégano (3.2 ha), Fray
240 124 Pacífico (1.6 ha), Perú (1.5 ha) and, Antonio Canales (0.5 ha).

242 125 Parks with an area greater than 10 ha were considered large urban green spaces,
243 126 considering that the total land area of Cáceres is approximately 17.7 km².

247 127 2.2. Questionnaire

249 128 This study was based on a questionnaire conducted in 2014 at selected sampling
250 129 points within green spaces. These points were selectively located in frequented areas that
251 130 contain different features and accommodate different uses, and collectively they cover
252 131 approximately the whole surface of the park (Fig. 1b). A similar number of questionnaires
253 132 were administered at each sampling site. The interviewers walked to the sampling point
254 133 of the green space and users were asked to participate in the survey. If one user refused
255 134 to participate, a new person was requested. Once the user was surveyed, the interviewers
256 135 moved to another sampling point. All selected interviewees were over 18 years old.
257 136 During the face-to-face questionnaire, interviewees were informed about the objectives
258 137 of the study and, they voluntarily agreed to participate. Each interview lasted
259 138 approximately 10–15 minutes. The response rate was 53%. Two hundred and ten
260 139 questionnaires were completed in large and small green spaces. Recent studies in urban
261 140 green spaces have used a similar sample size (Kothencz and Blaschke, 2017; Vujcic et
262 141 al., 2018). The power of the subsequent statistical tests was at least 0.8 for the sample size
263 142 obtained in this study (Cohen, 1988). The demographic characteristics of the respondents
264 143 were similar in both types of parks. The share of males and females was close to even
265 144 (53% females in large parks and 51% females in small parks). In addition, the age
266 145 structure did not present significant differences between the two types of green spaces (p
267 146 > 0.05 according to a Chi-squared test) as shown in Fig. 2.

268 147 Three categories were analysed in the questionnaire: satisfaction with green space
269 148 features (12 items), noise annoyance (8 items), and use of green spaces (6 items). All
270 149 items were evaluated using a 5-point Likert scale (0 - 'not at all' or 'never', 1 - 'a little'
271 150 or 'rarely', 2 - 'moderately' or 'sometimes', 3 - 'quite' or 'often', 4 - 'a lot' or 'very
272 151 often').

273 152 The following features were evaluated in the first category: cleanliness, air quality,
274 153 absence of noise, aesthetics, safety, users, conservation, location, size, shade, and groves.
275 154 Overall satisfaction was also assessed in one item. The level of user satisfaction with these

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155 features was questioned in this first category. These features were selected for their
156 relationship with social, environmental, or design aspects that influence overall
157 satisfaction with green spaces. Cleanliness, aesthetics, conservation, and groves influence
158 the visual assessment of a green space. Some studies include all of these features within
159 the aesthetic characteristic (McCormack et al., 2010). Absence of noise, air quality,
160 groves, and shade are features considered when assessing the environmental benefits of
161 green spaces (James et al., 2015). Location and size are design aspects that can influence
162 the use of green spaces (Schipperijn et al., 2010). Social aspects, such as the relationship
163 with users or security, were also considered. Crime and anti-social behaviour are
164 perceived risks from urban green spaces (WHO, 2016).

165 Parks are potentially quiet areas. Conserving quiet areas is an objective given priority
166 by the WHO (WHO, 2018). Rey-Gozalo and Barrigón-Morillas (2017) indicate that the
167 absence of noise is the most influential environmental feature determining the overall
168 perception of a quiet urban area. Thus, the degree of annoyance caused by the main sound
169 sources in these green spaces (road traffic, children, screams, construction sites,
170 maintenance services, animals, and water) was questioned in the second category of the
171 questionnaire. Users were also questioned about overall noise annoyance in urban green
172 parks. Moreover, sound levels were measured. Interviews and sound measurements were
173 carried out simultaneously. Equivalent sound level (L_{eq}) recorded with a binaural
174 recording device (Noise Book from Head Acoustics) was analysed for this study. The
175 guidelines of the ISO 1996-2 standard were followed for measuring during favourable
176 meteorological conditions and for locating the microphone (ISO 1996-2, 2007).

177 The frequency at which users conducted activities in these green spaces was analysed
178 in the last category of the questionnaire. The following activities were analysed: reading,
179 taking children outside, relaxing, exercising, walking, and talking.

180 *2.3. Statistical analysis*

181 The users' perception of the different variables was evaluated with a Likert ordinal
182 scale. Non-parametric tests were used because the condition of normality (Kolmogorov-
183 Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilks tests) was rejected. The Mann-Whitney test was used to
184 compare the users' perceptions of the different variables between both types of green
185 spaces. The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to compare perceptions of a green space among

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357 186 variables of the same category (satisfaction with features, noise annoyance, or use of
358 187 parks) and create homogeneous subsets.

360 188 This study also aimed to analyse the relationships among different variables. First,
361 189 the relationship between satisfaction with each feature and overall satisfaction with green
362 190 space was investigated. For this purpose, Kendall's tau-b was used. Then, a multivariate
363 191 analysis was conducted to analyse the features (independent variables) that contribute
364 192 significantly to explaining variability in overall satisfaction (dependent variable). For this
365 193 analysis, an ordinal logistic regression with forward and backward stepwise selection of
366 194 independent variables was used. Finally, relationships among satisfaction with green-
367 195 space features and green-space use were analysed (Kendall's tau-b). Pearson's correlation
368 196 coefficient was used in the relationship between the park area and the activities of
369 197 relaxing, exercising, and walking because the regression residuals did not present
370 198 significant differences with respect to a normal distribution.

378 199 Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 22 and R version 3.2.3.

381 200 **3. Results and discussion**

384 201 *3.1. Satisfaction with green-space features*

387 202 Users were quite satisfied with the features of the green spaces in Cáceres as shown
388 203 in Table 1. The average and median ratings given to the features were close to value 3
389 204 ('quite') or between values of 3 ('quite') and 4 ('a lot'), except for satisfaction with the
390 205 absence of noise (values between 2.5 and 3.0). Therefore, this high level of user
391 206 satisfaction shows that local administrations are interested in managing these urban
392 207 spaces. Despite this good assessment, do these two types of green spaces differ in users'
393 208 overall satisfaction and their satisfaction with features?

398 209 Users' perceptions of park features exhibited similarities in both types of green
399 210 spaces. The absence of noise was in the group of features rated lowest by users, and this
400 211 feature was even the least satisfactory feature in large parks (subset 'f' in Table 1). In
401 212 contrast, the location of green spaces was in the group of most valued features (subset 'a'
402 213 in Table 1).

406 214 Environmental (cleanliness, air, and noise), social (safety, users), and geographical
407 215 (location) features did not present significant differences in user satisfaction between the
408 216 two types of parks (Table 1). The selection of green spaces close to the city centre and

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415
416 217 their accessibility to the population within districts was corroborated with the perception
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418 218 of users. Features related to accessibility (proximity to residential areas, the public nature
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420 219 of parks, the existence of entrances through different pedestrian streets, the existence of
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422 220 parking and bus stops nearby, etc.) were similar in both types of parks. Cleaning and
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424 221 security services offered by local administrations are similar in all green spaces of
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426 222 Cáceres. There are also signs at the entrance to the green spaces with the rules of
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428 223 behaviour and regulations around opening and closing.

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430 224 The perception of air quality was one of the least valued features in both types of
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432 225 green space. This feature was significantly correlated with the absence of noise (Kendall's
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434 226 tau-b of 0.42 in large parks and 0.58 in small parks with a $p < 0.001$). This association
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436 227 may have been because road traffic represented the primary source of chemical and
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438 228 acoustic pollution in cities (Perez-Prada and Monzon, 2017). Current studies predict air
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440 229 pollutants using environmental noise measurements (Löbig and Weber, 2017). Sound
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442 230 levels recorded in the two types of green spaces were not significantly different (Fig. 3;
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444 231 $p > 0.05$ according to a Mann-Whitney test). Some places in large green spaces were
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446 232 further away from urban roads. Greater distance from road traffic can lead to lower levels
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448 233 of environmental pollution. However, the type of the surrounding urban road (Rey Gozalo
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450 234 et al., 2014) and the presence of other sound sources influence their acoustic situation
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452 235 (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2013).

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454 236 In contrast to the above features, satisfaction with aesthetics, conservation, size,
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456 237 groves, and shade in large green spaces was significantly higher than in small parks, as
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458 238 shown in Table 1. The difference in size between the two types of parks was perceived
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460 239 by those surveyed. Although the cleanliness of the two types of parks was perceived
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462 240 differently, the conservation of large green spaces presented greater satisfaction.
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464 241 Satisfaction with the aesthetic category was also perceived differently where the two
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466 242 groups of parks were concerned. Large parks had a greater variety of environments, even
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468 243 open-air museums, and this contributed to greater satisfaction. Perhaps satisfaction with
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470 244 groves and shade can influence some of these visual characteristics. There was a
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472 245 significant relationship among users' perception of groves, shade, and aesthetics ($p < 0.05$
246 according to the Kendall's tau-b).

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474 247 Greater land area provides the capacity to plant a greater number and variety of tree
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476 248 species. Groves generate shadows, and this association was perceived positively by users.
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478 249 Normalised differential vegetation index (NDVI) values of the green spaces investigated
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480 250 in this study are shown in Fig. 4. NDVI was taken from the open-access web interface

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251 Land Viewer (<https://eos.com/landviewer/>). This index was used to quantify green area
252 within the urban parks. Considering that the satellite image was taken during the summer
253 period (12th August 2014), this index also provided us with information relating to the
254 ground surface area covered by trees. Large parks had a higher NDVI in addition to
255 occupying a larger area (Fig. 4). The 2015 map of tree-cover density developed by the
256 EEA was also consulted. Layers with tree-cover density level in the range of 0–100% are
257 shown on the tree cover density map ([https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-
258 resolution-layers/forests/tree-cover-density/status-maps/2015](https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/forests/tree-cover-density/status-maps/2015)). The area of the layers
259 with a tree cover density greater than 40% was calculated in the two types of parks. In
260 large parks, 45% of the total area had a tree cover density higher than 40%. However,
261 only 30% of the total area of small parks had a tree cover density higher than 40%.
262 Differential satisfaction levels among users with the two types of green spaces were
263 justified according to both NDVI and tree-cover density.

264 Despite differences in levels of satisfaction with some features between the two types
265 of green spaces, users provided similar overall assessments (Table 1).

266 The next proposed research question was as follows: What is the relationship
267 between the perception of features and overall satisfaction with the green space?

268 Cleanliness, air quality, and the absence of noise were three of the four features that
269 presented the greatest correlation with overall satisfaction with both types of green spaces
270 (Table 2). Therefore, features related to environmental pollution were important to the
271 overall assessment of a park. Additionally, in both types of green space, user satisfaction
272 with size was not related to overall satisfaction. These results are of great relevance to the
273 design of urban green spaces. Size can limit the variety of installations, but if actions are
274 taken to improve some of the features (all the features were significantly correlated with
275 overall satisfaction with small green spaces except for size), user satisfaction will improve
276 regardless of park size.

277 The absence of noise was in the group of features with the lowest user satisfaction
278 with both types of green spaces. The sound level recorded in both types of green space
279 was similar to that of other Spanish parks (Calleja et al., 2017). The median sound level
280 obtained during the day exceeded the range of 45 to 55 dBA recommended by the EEA
281 for quiet areas (Fig. 3). Furthermore, satisfaction with the absence of noise was the most
282 correlated feature with overall satisfaction (Table 2).

283 As indicated above, some features were significantly interrelated. Therefore, the
284 bivariate relationships between individual features and overall satisfaction may be

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533
534 285 influenced by the effect of other features. In an attempt to detect these influences, a
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536 286 multivariate analysis was conducted using an ordinal logistic regression in each type of
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538 287 park (Table 3). The selection of independent variables was performed using the stepwise
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540 288 method and link function as logit. The values 0, 1, 2 and 3 shown in Table 3 are the values
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542 289 of the 5-point Likert scale used in the questionnaire. The value 4 is not shown in Table 3
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544 290 because it was the reference category. Some features also do not include values because
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546 291 they were not provided by users. Satisfaction with the absence of noise was selected
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548 292 among independent variables in both regression models. This result corroborates the
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550 293 importance of satisfaction with the absence of noise to explain the variability of overall
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552 294 satisfaction with both types of parks. The remaining features selected as independent
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554 295 variables differed between the two types of green spaces. The visual feature conservation
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556 296 was selected in large parks, while the social features of safety and user features were
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558 297 selected in small parks. In previous studies, the importance of visual and sound features
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560 298 was also demonstrated to influence overall perception of large parks (Qi et al., 2017).
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562 299 Peschardt et al. (2014) identified the importance of social features in small parks. In a
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564 300 logistic regression model, in addition to the social features (i.e., user and safety), when
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566 301 noise satisfaction was taken into account, the variability explained in overall satisfaction
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568 302 with small parks was high (McFadden $R^2 = 0.53$) (Table 3). Therefore, these features
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570 303 should receive special consideration by urban planners when designing small urban green
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572 304 spaces. For example, modifying the type and functionality of nearby roads or increasing
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574 305 the presence of people who ensure the safety and coexistence of users are some of the
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576 306 actions urban planners can take.

571 307 *3.2. Annoyance with sound sources*

573 308 The previous results indicate that users' satisfaction with the absence of noise was
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575 309 one of the most poorly rated features and that absence of noise was significantly
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577 310 correlated with overall satisfaction. To improve the perception of the absence of noise
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579 311 feature, it is important to analyse noise sources. Do the two types of green spaces differ
580
581 312 in how users perceive annoyance caused by different sources of noise?

582 313 The average and median of perceived annoyance with sound sources in both types of
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584 314 green spaces did not receive values greater than 2 'moderate annoyance' as shown in
585
586 315 Table 4. This result was predictable given that satisfaction with the absence of noise was
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588 316 rated 'moderate' to 'quite'. The most annoying sound sources (in decreasing order) in

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593 317 large green spaces were (subsets 'a' and 'b' in Table 4): animals (mainly barking),
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595 318 screams of children, and road traffic. Road traffic and screams were the most annoying
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597 319 sources in small green spaces. Road traffic and screams were important in both types of
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599 320 green spaces, though the annoyance with road traffic was significantly greater in small
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601 321 parks. The size of large green spaces implies a greater distance from the sources of road
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603 322 traffic sounds. Therefore, urban design of small green spaces should consider the
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605 323 functionality of nearby urban roads (Rey Gozalo et al., 2014).

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607 324 Annoyance due to barking (animals) in large green spaces was significantly greater
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609 325 than in small green spaces (Table 4). Large parks have specific canine areas. These areas
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611 326 represent approximately 5.2% of the total area of large parks
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613 327 (<http://sig.caceres.es/?lang=en>). This contributed to more dogs and, therefore, to this
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615 328 sound source. The annoyance of children was also significantly higher in large green
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617 329 spaces. Leisure activities for children in large green spaces were more diverse, and a
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619 330 greater percentage of users take their children outside to large green spaces. Of those
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621 331 interviewed in large parks, 32% brought children, while the equivalent value in small
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623 332 parks was only 24% of those interviewed. Liu et al. (2018a) show that surrounding speech
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625 333 and playing children were the most frequently perceived sound sources in parks of
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627 334 approximately 10 ha. Additionally, Liu et al. (2018b) found that dog barking was noisier
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629 335 than traffic in a large city park.

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631 336 The sound source categories of construction, maintenance, and water presented low
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633 337 levels of disturbance (subsets 'c', 'd', and 'e' in Table 4), and the two types of parks did
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635 338 not differ significantly in these categories. Studies show that the presence of water sources
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637 339 improves the soundscape (Ekman et al., 2015).

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639 340 Taking these results into account, city managers should consider the configuration of
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641 341 play and canine areas in large parks and the functionality of surrounding roads when
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643 342 designing small parks.

636 343 *3.3. Uses of the green spaces and relationship with their features*

638
639 344 In the design of green spaces, it is important that users can carry out activities that
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641 345 generate health benefits and that these activities are not exclusive to large parks. Do the
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643 346 two types of green spaces differ in the frequency of activities conducted by users? Is there
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645 347 any relationship between the frequency of these activities and the size of the green spaces?

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651
652 348 The activities of reading, talking, and taking children outside had similar frequencies
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654 349 in both types of green spaces as shown in Table 5. Children's play areas were more
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656 350 abundant in large green spaces (<http://sig.caceres.es/?lang=en>). However, if children's
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658 351 play areas are standardised to the total area of both types of parks, children's play areas
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660 352 accounted for 0.6% of the total area of large parks, but 2.6% in small parks. Additionally,
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662 353 users who bring children to the parks will usually talk to other users in the children's play
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664 354 area. Thus, for example, the activities of talking and bringing children were significantly
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666 355 correlated in large parks ($p < 0.05$, Kendall's tau-b = 0.19).

665 356 The most frequent activities in both types of green spaces were talking and walking
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667 357 (subsets 'a' in Table 5). Walking was more frequent in large parks than in small parks.
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669 358 However, an asymptotic relationship was found between the average walking frequency
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671 359 and park area, indicating that the frequency of this activity tended to stabilise at a certain
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673 360 size of green space (Fig. 5a). Above approximately 5 ha, the frequency of the walking
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675 361 activity plateaued in this study. In Fig. 5a, a logarithmic function was fit to the data. This
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677 362 size (> 5 ha) was also considered reasonable for physical activity in a previous study
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679 363 (Schipperijn et al., 2010). Walking is related to physical activity, but it also has a social
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681 364 component since it is not generally conducted in isolation.

679 365 Exercising and relaxing were also more frequent in large parks than in small ones.
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681 366 The frequency of these activities was positively correlated to the size of the park (Fig. 5b
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683 367 and Fig. 5c). In Fig. 5b and 5c, linear functions were fit to the data. The physical activity
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685 368 most frequently conducted by users was running and large green spaces had a greater
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687 369 length of paths (<http://sig.caceres.es/?lang=en>). The average length was 9.6 km in large
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689 370 parks and 3.2 km in small parks. Exercising was an activity more frequently performed
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691 371 by users younger than 60 years old. Watts et al. (2013) found a linear relationship between
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693 372 tranquillity and relaxation and subsequently a linear relationship between tranquillity and
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695 373 the size of the green space (Watts, 2017).

694 374 Closely related to these studied aspects, the last research question was analysed. Is
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696 375 the relationship between satisfaction with park features and the frequency of activities
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698 376 different for large parks than for small parks?

698 377 Reading was not significantly related to satisfaction with different park features
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700 378 (Table 6). Caution is warranted when interpreting this result since few users engaged in
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702 379 this activity in these green spaces (8%).

703 380 The frequency of taking children outside was positively correlated with user
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705 381 satisfaction with large parks and safety in small parks. Contact with other users in play

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711 382 areas was common, and safety was important. In addition, talking had a positive
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713 383 correlation with user satisfaction with both types of parks. The presence of other users is
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715 384 necessary for this activity to develop.

716 385 The low frequency of the relaxation activity in small parks influenced the lack of a
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718 386 relationship between this and other features. As shown in large green spaces, this activity
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720 387 was related to satisfaction with air quality and absence of noise. A larger park will
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722 388 promote a greater variety of environments. In fact, users look for places with a lower
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724 389 noise level in order to relax. A significant relationship between sound levels and the
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726 390 frequency of the relaxation activity was found in large parks ($p < 0.05$, Spearman's rho =
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728 391 -0.50). Therefore, actions that reduce road traffic noise could favour the frequency of this
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730 392 activity in small parks. Relaxation activities favour the improvement of health problems
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732 393 related to psychological disorders (stress, anxiety, etc.). These health problems are
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734 394 becoming more frequent in today's society.

735 395 Promotion of physical activity is an aim of today's societies in the face of growing
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737 396 health problems resulting from inactivity and poor eating habits. The frequency of
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739 397 physical activity in large parks was negatively related to user satisfaction. This indicates
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741 398 that despite these parks' adequate size, they were not designed for this purpose.
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743 399 Authorities should improve the design of large urban parks to promote physical activity.
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745 400 The main physical activity conducted was running, and there were no paths specifically
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747 401 marked for this activity. However, satisfaction with groves showed a positive correlation
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749 402 with physical activity in both types of park. This relationship was also shown in a previous
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751 403 study (McCormack et al., 2010). The lower NDVI and tree cover density in small parks
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753 404 influence the frequency of physical activity. Additionally, improvement to other visual
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755 405 and environmental features (e.g., air and conservation) that were ranked as offering lower
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757 406 satisfaction (Table 1) might encourage this activity.

758 407 Walking was positively correlated with satisfaction with a large number of features
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760 408 in small green spaces. Thus, encouragement of this activity in small parks requires an
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762 409 adequate overall design. The absence of noise and social characteristics such as safety, as
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764 410 well as overall satisfaction, presented the highest correlation values with walking in small
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766 411 parks. However, people walk in large parks without consideration of satisfaction with
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768 412 features, except having a good relationship with users. At a certain age, walking becomes
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770 413 the only viable physical activity for many. For this reason, the design of parks should
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772 414 encourage this activity in an era of worldwide ageing (UN, 2015).

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770 **4. Conclusions**
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773 416 A sociological study was undertaken to analyse the different features that define the
774 417 quality of urban green spaces with special attention given to the size of parks. From the
775 418 comparison of users' satisfaction with the features between the two types of parks and the
776 419 relationship between satisfaction with features and overall satisfaction, the following
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778 419 relationship between satisfaction with features and overall satisfaction, the following
779 420 results were obtained:

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781 421 - Satisfaction with large green spaces was significantly greater for 5 of 11 features
782 422 analysed (aesthetics, conservation, size, groves, and shade). Despite this, overall
783 423 user satisfaction was similar for both groups of parks.
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785 424 - Cleanliness, air quality, absence of noise, and conservation were significantly
786 425 correlated with overall satisfaction with large parks, but only noise and
787 426 conservation contributed significantly to explaining overall user satisfaction in an
788 427 ordinal logistic regression. On the other hand, all features analysed had a
789 428 significant relationship with the overall assessment of small parks except for size.
790 429 However, only noise, safety, and users were relevant in the ordinal logistic
791 427 regression. The absence of noise was the feature that explained the greatest
792 428 variability in overall satisfaction scores with both groups of parks.
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796 431
797 432 Some conclusions can be drawn from an analysis of the annoyance caused by noise
798 433 sources in both types of green spaces. Firstly, animals (mainly barking), screams, and
799 434 children were the most annoying noise sources in large green spaces. However, road
800 435 traffic was the most annoying source of noise in small green spaces. Secondly, if both
801 436 types of parks were compared, animals and children caused significantly more annoyance
802 437 in large parks, while road traffic was significantly more annoying in small parks.

803 438 The analysis of the frequency of activities conducted in both types of green spaces
804 439 and their relationship with users' satisfaction level with features of green spaces showed
805 440 the following:

- 806 441 - Walking and talking were the most frequent activities in both types of green
807 442 spaces, while talking and taking children outside had a similar frequency.
808 443 - Walking, relaxation, and exercising were significantly more frequent in large
809 444 parks. In fact, positive correlations were found between park area and the average
810 445 frequency of walking, relaxing, and exercising. However, the relationship found
811 446 between the average walking frequency and park area was asymptotic.
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- In both types of parks, a positive correlation was found between satisfaction with groves and exercising. The frequency of walking was only positively correlated with user satisfaction in large parks. However, this activity was also significantly correlated with environmental (noise, air, groves, and cleanliness) and social (safety and user) features in small parks.
- In large parks, the relaxation activity was positively correlated with users' satisfaction with air quality and absence of noise. However, the frequency of physical activity was negatively correlated with user satisfaction.

Finally, some recommendations are made to urban planners based on the conclusions of this study:

- Noise and conservation are features to be taken into account in order to increase the number of satisfied users in large parks. On the other hand, aspects such as noise, safety and coexistence of users should be considered in the design of small parks.
- An optimal configuration of the play and canine areas should be implemented with the aim of reducing noise annoyance in large parks. Designing an appropriate functionality for the streets surrounding small parks would help reduce noise annoyance.
- Authorities should ensure the existence of groves if they wish to promote physical activity in both types of parks. In addition, the design of specific running paths would benefit this activity in large parks.
- Analysing the users' perception of the park's features would be a point of support for the design of urban spaces.

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654 **Table 1**

655 Level of satisfaction with the features of urban green spaces, homogeneous subsets for
 656 the level of satisfaction in large and small parks, and an analysis of the significance of
 657 differences in the level of satisfaction between the two types of green spaces.

Feature	Scale of satisfaction (scale 0 – 4)				Homogeneous subsets ⁽¹⁾		P-value ⁽²⁾
	Large		Small		Large	Small	
	Mean	Median	Mean	Median			
Cleanliness	3.0	3.0	3.1	3.0	e	b, c	> 0.05
Air	2.8	3.0	2.8	3.0	e	c, d	> 0.05
Noise	2.5	2.5	2.7	3.0	f	d	> 0.05
Aesthetics	3.4	3.5	2.9	3.0	b, c, d	c, d	< 0.001
Safety	3.5	4.0	3.6	4.0	b, c	a	> 0.05
User	3.0	3.0	2.9	3.0	d	c, d	> 0.05
Conservation	3.3	3.0	2.9	3.0	c, d	c, d	< 0.001
Location	3.7	4.0	3.6	4.0	a	a	> 0.05
Size	3.8	4.0	3.3	3.0	a	b	< 0.001
Shade	3.5	4.0	2.9	3.0	a, b	c, d	< 0.001
Groves	3.6	4.0	2.9	3.0	a, b	c, d	< 0.001
Overall	3.2	3.0	3.2	3.0	–	–	> 0.05

658 ⁽¹⁾Kruskal-Wallis test

659 ⁽²⁾Mann-Whitney test

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1360 **660 Table 2**

1361
1362 661 Relationships between satisfaction with each feature and overall satisfaction with urban
1363
1364 662 green spaces (Kendall’s tau-b coefficient correlation).

Feature	Overall satisfaction	
	Large	Small
Cleanliness	0.23**	0.56***
Air	0.26**	0.58***
Noise	0.29***	0.60***
Aesthetics	0.17 ^{n.s.}	0.38***
Safety	0.09 ^{n.s.}	0.56***
User	0.12 ^{n.s.}	0.32***
Conservation	0.28**	0.36***
Location	0.03 ^{n.s.}	0.20*
Size	0.15 ^{n.s.}	0.08 ^{n.s.}
Shade	0.12 ^{n.s.}	0.41***
Groves	0.10 ^{n.s.}	0.40***

1386 663 * Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

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1388 664 ** Significant at $p \leq 0.01$

1389 665 *** Significant at $p \leq 0.001$

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1391 666 ^{n.s.} Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$)
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667 **Table 3**

668 Estimated parameters and coefficients of determination from an ordinal logistic
 669 regression between overall satisfaction (dependent variable) and satisfaction with features
 670 (independent variables) selected by the stepwise method.

Large green spaces			
		Estimate	Wald
Intercepts	Overall = 0	-7.6	31.6***
	Overall = 1	-6.1	38.3***
	Overall = 2	-5.4	36.0***
	Overall = 3	-1.0	2.5 ^{n.s.}
Coefficients	Conservation = 2	-3.5	12.9***
	Conservation = 3	-0.6	1.7 ^{n.s.}
	Noise = 1	-3.4	7.7**
	Noise = 2	-1.8	6.9**
	Noise = 3	-1.0	2.2 ^{n.s.}
R ² McFadden = 0.13			
Small green spaces			
		Estimate	Wald
Intercepts	Overall = 2	-11.6	32.9***
	Overall = 3	-6.5	18.8***
Coefficients	Noise = 1	-26.4	– ⁽¹⁾
	Noise = 2	-6.8	21.7***
	Noise = 3	-3.5	8.0**
	Safety = 3	-2.7	14.7***
	User = 2	-3.1	10.7**
	User = 3	-3.5	15.1***
R ² McFadden = 0.53			

671 ⁽¹⁾ Wald statistic is undefined because the error deviation is zero.

672 ** Significant at $p \leq 0.01$

673 *** Significant at $p \leq 0.001$

674 ^{n.s.} Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$)

675 **Table 4**

676 Level of annoyance with sound sources in urban green spaces, homogeneous subsets for
 677 the level of annoyance in large and small parks, and an analysis of the significance of the
 678 differences in the level of annoyance between the two types of green spaces.

Sound source	Level of annoyance (scale 0 – 4)				Homogeneous subsets ⁽¹⁾		P-value ⁽²⁾
	Large		Small		Large	Small	
	Mean	Median	Mean	Median			
Construction	0.3	0	0.3	0	d	d	> 0.05
Screams	1.2	1	1.1	1	a, b	b	> 0.05
Animals	1.4	1	0.2	0	a	e	< 0.001
Maintenance	0.6	0	0.6	1	c	c	> 0.05
Road traffic	1.0	1	1.4	1	b	a	< 0.001
Children	1.2	1	0.7	1	a, b	c	< 0.01
Water	0.4	0	0.2	0	c	e	> 0.05
Overall	1.2	1	1.1	1	–	–	> 0.05

679 ⁽¹⁾Kruskal-Wallis test

680 ⁽²⁾Mann-Whitney test

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1537 **681 Table 5**
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1539 682 Frequency of activities conducted by users in large and small urban green spaces.
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1541 683 Homogeneous subsets were used for the frequency of activities values, and an analysis of
1542 684 the significance of the differences in the level of frequency of activities between the two
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1544 685 types of green spaces.

Activity	Level of frequency (scale 0 – 4)				Homogeneous subsets ⁽¹⁾		P-value ⁽²⁾
	Large		Small		Large	Small	
	Mean	Median	Mean	Median			
Reading	0.3	0	0.1	0	d	d	> 0.05
Taking children outside	1.1	0	0.8	0	c	b, c	> 0.05
Relaxing	1.8	2	0.7	1	b	b	< 0.001
Exercising	1.3	1	0.5	0	c	c	< 0.001
Walking	2.9	3	2.0	2	a	a	< 0.001
Talking	2.4	3	2.4	3	a	a	> 0.05

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1562 686 ⁽¹⁾ Kruskal-Wallis test

1563 687 ⁽²⁾ Mann-Whitney test
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1596 **688 Table 6**
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1598 **689 Relationships among satisfaction with features and the frequency of activities in each type**
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1600 **690 of green space (Kendall's tau-b coefficient correlation).**

Features	Urban green-space use (Large/Small)					
	Reading	Taking children outside	Relaxing	Exercising	Walking	Talking
Cleanliness	–	–	–	–	– / 0.18*	–
Air	–	–	0.20* / –	– / 0.20*	– / 0.24**	–
Noise	–	–	0.17* / –	–	– / 0.33***	–
Aesthetics	–	–	–	–	– / 0.27**	–
Safety	–	– / 0.21*	–	–	– / 0.35***	–
User	–	0.19* / –	–	–0.54*** / –	0.39*** / 0.21*	0.69*** / 0.30***
Conservation	–	–	–	– / 0.21*	–	–
Location	–	–	–	– / 0.21*	–	–
Size	–	–	–	– / 0.21*	–	–
Shade	–	–	–	–	–	–
Groves	–	–	–	0.18* / 0.29**	– / 0.22*	–
Overall	–	–	–	– / 0.21*	– / 0.44***	–

1624 **691** * Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

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1626 **692** ** Significant at $p \leq 0.01$

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1628 **693** *** Significant at $p \leq 0.001$

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1630 **694** – Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$)

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697 b)

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Fig. 1. Location of the selected green spaces in the city of Cáceres (a) and sampling points within the studied green spaces (b).

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702 **Fig. 2.** Age structure of the selected samples in the two types of green spaces.

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Fig. 3. Equivalent continuous sound levels (dBA) measured in the small and large urban green spaces.

707 **Fig. 4.** Normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI) obtained from the parks studied.

708 This image was taken from the open-access web interface Land Viewer

709 (https://eos.com/landviewer/).

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717 **Fig. 5.** Relationships between park area and the average frequency of the following
 718 activities: walking (a), relaxing (b), and exercising (c).